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ABSTRACTS

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31. The Role of Distance Education in Decentralization of Higher Education - The Case of Iran

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Distance education system can facilitate the decentralization of higher education in Iran. It is suggested that one of the main reasons of deprivation of developing countries is the illogical distribution of higher education institutions, and the incapability of the governments of developing the advanced education universities in the remote areas or small towns.

Moreover, higher education imposes heavy expenditure on the national budget of such governments which in turn results in the low rate of growth of institutions or the creation of new universities in areas demanded.

Under such circumstances, Payame Noor University, within seven years of its operation, has succeeded to set up 117 local study centers which are decentralized in the sense that the authority delegated to them empowers these centers to run their activities in the most appropriate way. The result has been the provision of education and training in the regions that have been ignored by conventional higher education system.

32. University Reform : An Organizational Perspective

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'Restructuring' or 'organizational reform' of the universities, being a global problem, is a matter of serious concern for India too since alike most other Third World countries, our university structure also fails to match with the needs and demands of the ever-changing economic and societal environment. While some hundred or thousand papers on the need for restructuring have been produced, the issue still remains to be purely a matter of academic discussion only. Besides the honest and sincere effort of a number of prominent academicians and educationists, Government at the Central, as well as, at the State levels have appointed a number of Committees and Commissions to bring in the required changes. All such Committees and Commissions have offered many recommendations and most of them are yet to be implemented. As a consequence, the structure remains as it has emerged under the colonial regime.

The term 'structure' itself signifies relatively stable relationship. Besides, structure of governance, for an organization, remains unchanged only when it assures satisfaction of the most dominant coalitions within it. Obviously, the present structure of governance of the universities assure a high degree of participants' satisfaction and as a result, despite occasional discussion by the academic elites, the structure remains as it was.

The present paper, after defining the concept of 'structural reform', will concentrate on the process of reform from an organizational perspective and finally will seek to locate the possible road-blocks to structural reform of the universities.

University Reform : An Organizational Perspective

Anubrata Datta

21st century, for the Indians, might be a century of transition. The pressure of globalization has paved the way of transition from a mixed economy to a market economy. Within the set up of a market economy, survival of any kind of human institution depends upon its ability to adapt the environmental challenges and no institution can survive if it fails to maintain a balance between the tradition and change (Elton, L. 1981). Traditionally, universities have an 'Ivory Tower' image - which was rather isolated from the rest of the other social organizations. By tradition, universities were communities of teachers and scholars and were largely financed by the State irrespective of satisfying any kind of performance criteria. Until the mid-twentieth century, universities, by and large, were elite institutions having a lower enrollment and a high level of scholarly standards (Husen, T., 1991). During the early 1950s, there was a radical change in the ecology of higher education in the developed countries and the 'Ivory Tower' image has been challenged by a rather utilitarian conception where the basic aim of a university has been shifted towards equipping the students with the right kind of knowledge and skills that are necessary to tackle practical problems which they will be confronting in their future lives. Thus, in the developed countries, the universities have changed from elite to mass and then mass to universal institutions (Trow, M., 1973).

However, the situation is somehow different in case of the Third World countries. For example, the Indian universities still have an inclination towards rigidity and conservatism. The initial structure of the Indian universities were developed by the British following the model of London University and perhaps due to its 'colonial legacy', there exists a strong inertial tendency as almost the same structure prevails even today leading to the following unhealthy features :

- Indian universities prefer remaining as 'Ivory Towers' with the sole objective of escaping performance measurement of any kind.
- As organizations, Indian universities are preoccupied in creating and maintaining an elitist institutional image requiring no accountability.
- They neglect social relevance of education while striving for autonomy.
- Emphasize theoretical knowledge neglecting practical experiences.
- Prefer legitimized action than performance measurement on the basis of some objective criteria.
- Depend more on grants and subsidies from the governmental sources rather than striving for economic self-sufficiency.
- Prefer to be governed following the model of "professional feudalism" unlike a 'rational' organization directed towards well - defined goals of maximizing expected values.

In view of the above, it is rather obvious that to cope with the social, economic and technological challenges of the 21st century, Indian universities must have to adapt the necessary changes. Thus, for the Indian universities, the most important agenda of action on the eve of the 21st century, might be a reform.

University Reform : What is it?

While there is a consensus amongst the academicians regarding the need for reforming the Indian universities, there are controversies regarding the exact area of reform. A section of the academicians are in favor of curricular reform. They emphasize that course structures are to be reformed so as to make the curricula market-need oriented. Some others highlight reforming the present method of teaching. Still, according to a section of experts, reform essentially means redesigning the administrative structure of the universities. They are of the view that unless and until the structure of governance of a university is altered, other changes like change in curricula or instructional methods can not be implemented properly. Since the structure of governance of a university is the vital most determinant of the internal processes, the present paper defines university reform as the process of introducing planned changes in the structure of governance of a university so as to assure its survival in a highly dynamic environment. Structure, in general, refers to the relatively stable interrelationships (Johnson, 1960) within the design of an organization through which the institution is being administered (Chandler, A.D. Jr., 1962). Structure of governance, in case of a university, refers to the existing network of roles and responsibilities of the different administrative organs and functionaries as emerged over time through continuous interaction between the contextual factors, environmental forces and institutional forces. Thus, university reform is essentially directed towards redesigning the existing hierarchical pattern through which a university at present is being administered.

In this connection, it is to be noted that growth of the structure, by itself, is not a reform. Horizontal or vertical expansion of the structure of governance is merely a growth symptom since a reform is rather a wholesome change in the configuration of the structure involving shifting of formal authority into some new directions.

The Organizational Perspective

University reform, being a popular topic for academic discussion, has been viewed from different theoretical perspectives. For the political scientists, a reform can be viewed as an outcome of interactions among different social groups participating in the system. However, the present paper seeks to develop a conceptual framework of the reform process and the obstacles thereof from an organizational perspective. Of course there is no consensus even amongst the organization theorists about the goals of a reform. For example, contingency theorists argue that reform or structural changes are necessary to match the organization structure with the technology - environment pairs (Thomson, G.D., 1967, Lawrence & Lorsh, 1967). According to the resource-dependence theorists, reform is required to neutralize sources of environmental uncertainty (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978). Marxists may argue that reform or structural changes are instruments in the hands of the capitalists to enhance control over the workers (Burawoy, 1979). However, the present paper seeks to highlight that as rational organizations, universities should always focus on the center-stage activity of the system for which it has been created, viz., teaching and research and towards these ends in view, the goal behind a reform proposal might be any one or a combination of the following :

1. Making the system customers' (students') need oriented
2. Creating accountability among teachers;
3. Assuring excellence through quality improvement;
4. Ensuring participation towards democratization;
5. Establishing linkages with industries for attaining financial self-sufficiency.

University Reform as a Process

As a process, university reform can be defined as the institutionalization of an internally generated or environmentally imposed design of the structure of governance altering the existing one. According to Altbach (1980), university reform can be defined as a "... combination of political process with academic goals and interests...". Every reform proposal, within the university system, should be directed towards an academic goal. But whether the objective is academic or administrative, a reform involves substantial changes in both the formal and informal power structure and the consequences of such changes are always controversial. Since institutionalization of a reform proposal will result into the down gradation of status as well as, canalization of scarce institutional resources into some new directions from the pet projects of the existing power elite, they will be the ultimate victims. Those who will be losing their formal or informal authority are always against a reform movement and might have a tendency to devote themselves in propagating and convincing the probable adverse effects of the reform proposal. Hence, institutionalization of a reform proposal is entirely a political process involving continuous conflict and negotiation. Hefferlin (1969) observed that the history of reform is full of example of compromise between the power elite within an institution. A university is, no doubt, a coalition of a diverse spectrum of interest groups and as such, consensus within a university is always the result of compromise. Obviously, compromise at almost every step enhances the acceptability of the reform proposal. But at the same time, it cannot be denied that compromise between the conflicting interest groups tend to dilute the basic purpose or objective for which the original reform proposal was initiated. As such, many of the reform proposals, when actually implemented lack relevance.

University Reform : Source of Impetus

University reform is a complex process since it's implications are far reaching and multidimensional. Hence, reform is never an automatic process. Only a series of pressures from within and outside the university can assure the successful implementation of a reform proposal. In reality, the ultimate implementation of a reform proposal depends upon the relative strength of the initiator(s) of the reform movement and not on the relative worth or effectiveness of the proposal. In case of the universities, the sources of impetus may either be external or internal.

Among the external sources - which can provide impetus to a reform movement in case of the Indian universities, Government is the most dominant one since Government bears the brunt of expenditure of the universities. Government usually appoints some official committees or commissions for suggesting the desired changes and surprisingly, most of the recommendations of such committees or commissions are ignored except those associated with the pay scale or salary level of the faculty (Altbach, P.G., 1972, p.256). Some other reforms, which have yet been implemented, are purely political in nature since they have only assured political interventions into the university system rather than improving the efficiency or effectiveness of the system. However, in Sweden, the university reform proposals were initiated and implemented by the Government (Altbach, 1980, p.1). Even, public demand for access to higher education or market demand for trained manpower or an economic reform initiated by the Government may ultimately provide impetus to a reform movement.

Among the internal sources of stimuli, students' needs and demands have a major potential. West Germany experienced a series of reforms in the university system out of the discontent of the students who even have participated in developing the reform plans (Altbach, 1980, p.2). Again, in France, the students' revolt of 1968 has radically decentralized the universities. In Japan, the student unrest in 1960s stimulated reform. Unfortunately, the multi-

party unionism of the Indian students perhaps protected the education system from reform pressures of the students.

The vital most source of a potential reform movement might be the faculty members of a university since in India, in the name of autonomy, they are the real decision - makers. Refusal or acceptance of a reform proposal is ultimately a matter of choice of the faculties. However, in India for the faculties, structure has emerged as a term on which only blames are shifted even without realizing the fact that the faculties are the main components of the structure. A majority of the academicians are very much enthusiastic in discussing the needs for reform or restructuring of the higher education system but perhaps none of them is ready to face the consequences. McIver and Page (1955) observed that if a structure persists over a long period of time, it is because of the interests and attitudes of the social beings associated with it. Obviously, the present structure assures a high level of faculty satisfaction and as such, they are keen in protecting the structure from all possible reform pressures.

University Reform : Some Major Constraints

The consequences of a reform are far-reaching and multidimensional and consequently, constraints are also numerous. Some of the barriers are within the universities and some others are external to the system. External obstacles include social, economic and political factors and forces. For example, in India, the educated middle class, out of their own interest of opening up their career, exert substantial pressure against a reform in the fee structure of the universities. Having a good control and command over the political power, the middle class is in favor of a highly subsidized higher education system through which they can improve their careers, even though, atleast a majority of them are capable of paying for the fees and charges.

Social, economic or political forces, however influential, are external to the universities and the present paper seeks to concentrate on the organizational aspects involving the internal obstacles to reform. Internal constraints can be elaborated as under :

(A) Organizational Constraints :

Universities can be viewed as 'environment servicing organizations' (Ansoff, I., 1979, p.10) since they are basically conservative in that sense, they have a general tendency to resist change or reform. Universities as organizations, systematically eliminate reform that may incorporate inspection, evaluation or control over the instructional activity (Callahan, 1962) since 'close supervision of instructional activities and output may uncover inconsistencies and inefficiencies' (Meyer, J.W., et. al., 1981).

Over time, educational organizations have emerged to bring about the "...process of education under a socially standardized set of institutional categories" and not for rationalizing the process of imparting education. So, the structure is 'loosely coupled', i.e., the structure is not properly aligned with the task or technology of imparting education (Weick, 1976) and as such, educational organizations are not enthusiastic in improving the quality, efficiency or effectiveness through reforming the structure.

(B) Structural Constraints :

The structure of the Indian universities, which was originally designed by the British following the structure of the London University, itself resist reform since structure, by definition, represents relatively stable relationships. Out of it's structural inertia', university structures respond relatively slowly to adapt environmental changes (Hannan & Freeman,

1984) and as such, either reform movement fails or the reform proposal lose it's relevance due to the slow pace of adaptation.

Besides, within the present pattern of university governance, there are a number of large sized committees at each level with a good deal of divided responsibility. Consequently, the power of decision - making, as well as, of decision implementing are pluralistic. Again, the structure is vertically fragmented. Altogether, the structure is not suitable for implementing changes or reforms.

(C) Procedural Constraints :

Modification or alteration of the administrative structure of an Indian university requires an amendment of the Act, Statute and Ordinances of the concerned university and an amendment is rather a highly bureaucratic process. University Acts specify the grounds on which an amendment of the Statute or Ordinances can be made. In case of the Statute, the Executive Council will make a draft in its own motion or being directed by the Court. The draft is to be submitted to the Court for consideration and approval by an agreement of majority of the members present. Finally, the draft shall be presented to the Chancellor for assent and shall come into effect on being assented to by the Chancellor in consultation with the concerned Minister. Obviously, the process of amendment requires the active support of a majority of the Executive Council and Court members and the ultimate assent giving authority is the Chancellor who is supposed to take the advice of the concerned Minister.

If a reform proposal is designed internally by a teacher of a university and if the initiator is very much keen in implementing his/her proposal, he/she will have to fight a long series of bitter battles to convince the merits of the reform proposal to the dominant coalitions at the different levels of the structure. At each level, he/she will have to face strong opposition and severe criticisms since most of the university teachers are never ready to accept or welcome a change or reform proposal particularly when it has been initiated by a colleague. Thus, the present method of amendment containing a highly democratic channel is a strong barrier to reform.

When the reform proposal has been imposed by an external authority like the UGC, it becomes a headache for the top level executives like the Vice Chancellor to make it acceptable to the internal participants. Sincere effort of the top-level executives to adopt a reform proposal does not necessarily guarantee its implementation. The reform proposal must have to be acceptable to a number of committees containing an wide variety of member-orientations. Otherwise, the internal participants have the legitimate right to agitate against the reform proposal – which may ultimately result into a chaos or a compromise. Thus the procedural maze itself is a strong obstacle to reform in case of the universities.

(D) Internal Political Constraints :

Indian universities are particularly famous for a multidimensional internal politics. There are four major groups – the teachers, administrative officers, *Karmacharies* and the students. Multi-party unionism within each of the above four categories have fragmented them into a large number of sub-groups. Besides explicit politics, there are a good deal of tacit understandings and personality clashes at the individual level. In the absence of harmony and congruence amongst the internal participants, it is not easy to implement a reform a proposal. Hannan & Freeman (1984) observed that when organizational members have diverse interests, outcomes depend heavily on the internal politics and on the balance of power and in most cases, such outcomes fail to match rationality with the changing environment.

Academic elite within the university system seek to escape reforms since they are not sure about the ultimate outcome of a reform movement and they are afraid of losing the current benefits and status. Thus, when a reform proposal is imposed by an external authority like the UGC, the internal process of conflict – negotiation – compromise starts to modify the reform proposal substantially so as to make it acceptable to the majority of the dominant coalitions associated with the power structure. Over time, it has become the sacred duty of the internal power elite to modify the externally imposed reform proposals into some harmless paper works, which, of course, assures their political existence.

(E) Values & Attitudinal Constraints :

Even in the absence of financial self-sufficiency, Indian universities are given an autonomous status which signifies that they are free to make their own decisions and can handle matters internally (Warnock, M. 1992). Some large sized committees have been prescribed for internal decision making and these committees are, by and large, teacher-dominated. Thus, preferences of the teachers regarding desired organizational outcomes or values and attitudes of them play a dominant role in accepting or rejecting a reform proposal. Hage & Dewar (1973) observed that the values of the elite in an organization who holds high level positions by way of their formal or informal authority are the strongest defenders of the *status quo*.

A section of the academic elite like to preserve the existing structure as a symbol of institutional reputation and prestige and as such, they resist reforms. Again, academic elite are basically conservative and relies on known methods (Evans, 1967). Thus, they have a tendency to oppose or at best reject a reform proposal since it may change the existing pattern of distribution of power, privilege and rewards.

Besides, Indian teachers were enjoying a higher social status. Teaching was a highly respected profession though the salaries or pay structures of the teachers were low as compared to other professions demanding similar qualifications (Chauhan, C.P.S., 1990, p.131). Higher social status has contributed a lot to make the teachers reluctant to accept ideas of others and as such, it became difficult to convince them regarding the need for implementing a reform.

Even, after the revision of pay scales of the teachers in 1973 and afterwards, teaching has become an attractive profession and enhanced economic status of the teachers has resulted into a declining social status. Waning social respect is an emerging threat for the teachers, which also made them afraid of taking the risk of a reform involving the possibilities of status down-gradation.

To conclude, reform obstacles percolate into the Indian University system through the process of recruitment of the educational administrators. The present method of recruitment, which has proved itself successful in eliminating reforms, has a strong preference towards experience as a selection criteria rather than creativity, initiative or innovative aptitudes. Besides, the traditional ‘experience-oriented’ reward system fails to encourage innovative ideas or initiative from the existing participants. Unless and until the present method of selection and the reward systems are changed, it will be difficult even for the UGC to implement a reform. In this connection, after the introduction of the New Education Policy, 1986, the UGC has appointed a Committee Towards New Educational Management which has submitted it’s report in 1990 suggesting a number of alternative structures for improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the Indian university system and following the Indian tradition, most of the suggestions remained unimplemented. If, even the UGC recommended reforms are escaped or manipulated, will it be possible for the Indian universities to encounter the challenges of the 21st Century?

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